

EYLER TENGLAMASI VA UNI YECHIH

Kenjayev T. A¹, Bakirova M.N.²

¹DTPI Oliy matematika kafedrasi o‘qituvchisi, ²4 bosqich talabasi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada muhim differensial tenglama - Eyer tenglamasining mohiyati, xususiyatlari va uning turlari, Eyer tenglamasi yechimini topish usullari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: differensial tenglama, Eyer tenglamasi, xususiy yechim, umumiy yechim.

Abstract. This article discusses the essence, properties and types of an important differential equation - Euler's equation, as well as methods for finding solutions to Euler's equation.

Keywords: differential equation, Euler's equation, particular solution, general solution.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются сущность, свойства и виды важного дифференциального уравнения — уравнения Эйлера, а также методы нахождения решений уравнения Эйлера.

Ключевые слова: дифференциальное уравнение, уравнение Эйлера, частное решение, общее решение.

1-ta'rif. Ushbu

$$x^n y^{(n)} + a_1 x^{n-1} y^{(n-1)} + \dots + a_{n-1} x y' + a_n y = 0 \quad (1)$$

ko‘rinishdagi differensial tenglamaga Eyer tenglamasi deyiladi. Bu yerda $a_i = \text{const}$, $i = 1, n$.

Bu differensial tenglamani

$$x = e^t \quad (2)$$

almashtirish yordamida n — tartibli bir jinsli o‘zgarmas koeffitsientli differensial tenglamaga keltirish mumkin. Haqiqatan ham (2) almashtirish (1) differensial tenglamani tartibini va chiziqililigini saqlab qoladi. Quyidagi hisoblashlarni bajaramiz:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = e^t, \frac{dt}{dx} = e^{-t}$$

$$y' = \frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{dy}{dt} \cdot \frac{dt}{dx} = \frac{dy}{dt} e^{-t} = e^{-t} \frac{dy}{dt}$$

$$x y' = e^t e^{-t} \frac{dy}{dt} = \frac{dy}{dt}$$

$$y'' = \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{dy}{dx} \right) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dy}{dx} \right) \frac{dt}{dx} = e^{-t} \frac{d}{dt} \left(e^{-t} \frac{dy}{dx} \right) \frac{dt}{dx} = e^{-2t} \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} - \frac{dy}{dt} \right)$$

$$x^2 y'' = e^{2t} e^{-2t} \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} - \frac{dy}{dt} \right) = \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} - \frac{dy}{dt} \right)$$

.....

$$y^{(k)} = \frac{d^{(k)} y}{dx^{(k)}} = e^{-kt} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\alpha_1 \frac{dy}{dt} + \alpha_2 \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} + \dots + \alpha_k \frac{d^k y}{dt^k} \right)$$

$$x^{(k)}y^{(k)} = e^{kt}e^{-kt} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\alpha_1 \frac{dy}{dt} + \alpha_2 \frac{d^2y}{dt^2} + \dots + \alpha_k \frac{d^ky}{dt^k} \right) = \alpha_1 \frac{dy}{dt} + \alpha_2 \frac{d^2y}{dt^2} + \dots + \alpha_k \frac{d^ky}{dt^k} \quad (3)$$

Bu yerda $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k$ – o‘zgarmas sonlar. Topilgan (3) formulalardan foydalanib (1) differensial tenglamani quyidagi

$$\frac{d^ny}{dt^n} + b_1 \frac{d^{n-1}y}{dt^{n-1}} + \dots + b_{n-1} \frac{dy}{dt} + b_n y \quad (4)$$

ko‘rinishdagi n – tartibli o‘zgarmas koeffitsiyentli chiziqli differensial tenglamaga keladi.

Bu yerda b_n o‘zgarmas sonlar. (4) differensial tenglamaning xususiy yechimlari $y(t) = e^{kt}$ almashtirish yordamida topiladi. Berilgan (1) differensial tenglamaning xususiy yechimlarini ushbu

$$y(x) = e^{kt} \quad (5)$$

almashtirish yordamida topish mumkin. Quyidagi

$$y' = ke^{k-1}$$

$$y'' = k(k-1)e^{k-1}$$

.....

$$y^{(n)} = k(k-1) \dots (k-n+1)e^{k-1}$$

hosilalarni (2.2.24) differensial tenglamaga qo‘yib

$$k(k-1) \dots (k-n+1) + a_1 k(k-1) \dots (k-n+2) + \dots + a_{n-1} k + a_n = 0 \quad (6)$$

algebraik tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Bu algebraik tenglamaga (1) differensial tenglamaning xarakteristik tenglamasi deyiladi va u (4) differensial tenglamaning xarakteristik tenglamasi bilan mos tushadi.

I. Agar (6) xarakteristik tenglamaning ildizlari k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n haqiqiy va har xil bo‘lsa (1) Eyler differensial tenglamasining umumiy yechimi

$$y(x) = C_1 x^{k_1} + C_2 x^{k_2} + \dots + C_n x^{k_n} \quad (2.2.30)$$

ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi.

II. Agar (6) xarakteristik tenglamaning ildizlari k_1, k_1, \dots, k_1 har xil ildizlarga ega bo‘lib, ular r_1, r_1, \dots, r_n karrali $r_1 + r_2 + \dots + r_n = n$ bo‘lsa, u holda (1) Eyler differensial tenglamasining umumiy yechimi

$$y(x) = x^{r_1} P_1(\ln x) + x^{r_2} P_2(\ln x) + \dots + x^{r_n} P_n(\ln x) \quad (7)$$

ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi. Bu yerda $P_n(t), t = \ln x$ ixtiyoriy rn - darajali ko‘phad.

III. Agar (6) xarakteristik tenglama $k = \alpha + i\beta, \beta = 0$ ko‘rinishdagi r karrali kompleks ildizga ega bo‘lsa, u holda (1) Eyler differensial tenglamasi uchun ushbu

$$x^\alpha \cos(\beta \ln x), x^\alpha (\ln x) \cos(\beta \ln x), \dots, x^\alpha (\ln x)^{r-1} \cos(\beta \ln x)$$

$$x^\alpha \sin(\beta \ln x), x^\alpha (\ln x) \sin(\beta \ln x), \dots, x^\alpha (\ln x)^{r-1} \sin(\beta \ln x)$$

funksiyalar xususiy yechim bo‘ladi.

Misol. Quyidagi

$$x^3 y''' + xy' - y = 0 \quad (1)$$

Eyler tenglamasini umumiy yechimini toping.

Yechish. (1) tenglamani yechish uchun dastlab

$$x = e^t \quad (2)$$

belgilash kiritamiz. (2) tenglikdan

$$t = \ln x$$

kelib chiqadi. (3) tengliklardan foydalanib

$$y' = e^t y'_t, y'' = e^{-2t} (y''_t - y'_t)$$

$$y' = e^{-3t} (y'''_t + 3y''_t + 2y'_t) \quad (3)$$

hosil qilamiz. (3) tengliklarni (1) tenglamaga qo‘yib

$$e^{3t} e^{-3t} (y'''_t + 3y''_t + 2y'_t) + e^t e^{-t} y'_t - y = 0$$

$$y''' + 3y'' + 2y' + y = 0 \quad (4)$$

o‘zgarmas koeffitsiyentli chiziqli differensial tenglamani hosil qilamiz. (4) tenglamani yechish uchun

$$y = e^{kt}$$

belgilashdan foydalanib

$$k^3 - 3k^2 + 3k + 1 = 0 \quad (5)$$

k ga nisbatan algebraik tenglamaga kelamiz. (5) tenglamaning ildizi

$$k_1 = k_2 = k_3 = 1$$

bo‘lgani uchun unga mos bo‘lgan (4) tenglamaning xususiy yechimlari

$$y_1 = e^t, y_2 = te^t, y_3 = t^2 e^t \text{ ya'ni}$$

$$y_t = C_1 e^t + C_2 t e^t + C_3 t^2$$

$$y_t = e^t (C_1 + C_2 t + C_3 t^2)$$

bo‘ladi. (1) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi esa

$$y = x(C_1 + C_2 \ln x + C_3 \ln x^2)$$

bo‘ladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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